

Toward an Intersectional Legal Framework: Deconstructing and Reforming the Law on Gender Violence in the State of Mexico

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Abstract (English):

This preprint presents a theoretical and legal proposal to incorporate the intersectional approach into the Law on Women's Access to a Life Free from Violence in the State of Mexico. Based on a critical analysis of the epistemic and legal limitations of the current normative framework, the paper defines *intersectional violence* as a distinct legal and analytical category. It argues that the current legal definition of gender-based violence—premised on a universal female subject—fails to account for the multiple, overlapping structures of oppression affecting Indigenous, racialized, poor and sexually dissident women. Accordingly, the proposal introduces several original theoretical concepts: *intersectional violence*, *intersectional justice*, *positive*, *negative*, and *hybrid intersectionality*, and the *methodological principles of intersectional categories*, which offer more precise tools for identifying, analyzing, and addressing complex forms of violence.

The proposal is grounded in an epistemic critique of the abstract universalism of modern law, drawing on the works of Judith Butler, Miranda Fricker, Donna Haraway, Sandra Harding, María Lugones, and Boaventura de Sousa Santos. It denounces *intersectional epistemic injustice*, understood as the exclusion of situated knowledge, categories, and experiences from dominant normative frameworks. It argues that true mainstreaming of intersectionality requires clear legal definitions, operational categories, and a profound revision of normative system.

Keywords:

intersectional violence; intersectional justice; intersectional injustice; intersectional episteme; situated justice; legal reform; gender-based violence; epistemic injustice; decolonial feminism; Global South; Mexican law.

Statement of Purpose

This legislative initiative aims to explicitly incorporate the intersectional approach into the Law on Women's Access to a Life Free of Violence in the State of Mexico. It acknowledges that the violence women face does not occur uniformly, but is exacerbated by structural

inequalities such as social class, race, sexual orientation, gender identity, disability, age, geographic location, among others.

Although the current law refers to intersectionality in limited terms — for example, Article 3, Section X mentions the concept as an analytical tool, and includes a “differential” approach in Section VI, complemented by interculturality in Section IX — these mentions are superficial and do not develop a methodology or guidelines capable of addressing the complexity of violence. Thus, it reproduces the logic that renders invisible or trivializes the differentiated experiences of Indigenous, Afro-descendant, disabled, trans, sex worker, and migrant women, among others.

Despite political commitments made by the Mexican state — such as constitutional reforms on the rights of Indigenous and Afro-descendant peoples and communities, or presidential speeches recognizing the vulnerability of certain groups of women — a significant omission persists: the absence of a comprehensive, operational conceptual framework on intersectionality, essential for mainstreaming this approach into public policies, programs, and state regulations.

This omission results in *intersectional epistemic injustice*: the legal framework’s inability to recognize the multiple and simultaneous forms of oppression that intersect in women’s experiences, and the persistence of a discourse that, although progressive in appearance, lacks depth in analyzing hierarchies and exclusions. The proposed transformation is not merely terminological but profoundly structural, as it involves moving from a monocausal “gender-based violence” approach to one that articulates *intersectional violence* in its substantive, gender-based, and epistemic dimensions, grounded in critical, situated, and decolonial frameworks.

This initiative builds on recent conceptual advances proposing intersectional categories as analytical tools capable of overcoming monocausal reductionism. It is based on the methodological principle that an intersectional category is not the sum of its parts, but a relational and dynamic entity — a superposition of oppression factors — whose essence is not lost by recognizing, from a situated observation, the relative weight of some of its components. This perspective aligns with intersectional epistemic justice, essential for countering the invisibilization of multiple violences experienced by many women in the state.

The proposed reform seeks to strengthen the local legal framework so that the State of Mexico may become a national leader in recognizing, preventing, and eradicating both gender-based and intersectional violence, facilitating the mainstreaming of intersectionality as a principle of structural justice.

It is imperative that legislation moves beyond reproducing vulnerability stereotypes and a homogeneous view of gender, and instead ensures comprehensive protection for women in all their diversity through robust, operational definitions — such as those proposed herein. Only through deep intersectional mainstreaming can true

intersectional substantive justice be achieved — one that not only acknowledges the multiple forms of violence but also provides the conceptual and legal tools for their prevention, response, and redress.

SPECIAL SECTION: INTERSECTIONAL VIOLENCE

Article X. Principle of Intersectionality

This Law recognizes the intersectional approach as a guiding principle in the interpretation, implementation, and evaluation of public policies aimed at preventing, addressing, punishing, and eradicating violence against women. Competent authorities must apply this approach in all stages of the design, execution, and evaluation of programs, policies, regulations, and actions, transversally.

Article X Bis. Definition of the Intersectional Approach

Intersectional Episteme is understood as the set of hermeneutic and reasoning resources (concepts, judgments, arguments) that make it possible to understand, make visible, and respond to subjects, groups, and/or communities situated at the dynamic intersection of structures of oppression and/or privilege. This episteme breaks with monocausal and linear frameworks of analysis and proposes a relational, situated, and critical perspective on social reality.

For the purposes of legal interpretation and public policy, the following distinction is made:

I. **Intersectionality lato sensu**: Refers broadly to the general interrelation of oppression and/or privilege, understood as the relational totality of interwoven systems of power that shape social experiences.

II. **Intersectionality stricto sensu**: Manifests in three specific forms:

- a) **Positive intersectionality**: When the analysis focuses on the privileges enabled by the intersection of categories.
- b) **Negative intersectionality**: When the analysis focuses exclusively on the oppressions generated by such intersections.
- c) **Hybrid intersectionality**: When the simultaneous combination of oppressions and privileges is analyzed, recognizing their dynamic and contextual coexistence.

For the purposes of this Law, the intersectional approach to violence against women is understood as the perspective that recognizes that women may experience multiple,

simultaneous, and interwoven forms of discrimination and violence, arising from the interaction of structural conditions such as gender, class, race, ethnicity, age, sexual orientation, gender identity, disability, migratory status, or membership in Indigenous or Afro-descendant communities, and/or other factors relevant to the specific context in which women live.

We understand violence as an aggression that causes harm and/or injury. Therefore, the definitions of intersectional violence presented herein follow the logic of the negative type of intersectionality in the *stricto sensu* sense. However, the other two subtypes (positive and hybrid) may be used as auxiliary epistemic tools in the interpretation and understanding of the interrelated forms of violence experienced by the most vulnerable people in society.

Article X Ter. Substantive Intersectional Violence

Substantive intersectional violence is defined as the harm and/or injury caused to individuals, groups, or communities as a result of the simultaneous interaction of two or more systems of oppression, including but not limited to gender, race, ethnicity, social class, sexual orientation, gender identity, disability, or age. This violence affects people differently depending on their position within these intersections and cannot be adequately understood through monocausal categories of analysis.

Article X Quater. Intersectional Epistemic Violence

Intersectional epistemic violence is defined as the harm and/or injury — intentional or not, by action or omission — caused to individuals, groups, or communities when their situated experiences, shaped by multiple forms of oppression, are addressed using

theoretical or institutional frameworks that invisibilize, distort, minimize, trivialize, or deny them. This form of violence hinders the full recognition of interwoven realities and constitutes a form of structural cognitive exclusion.

Article X Quinquies. Intersectional Gender-Based Violence

Intersectional gender-based violence is defined as the harm and/or injury resulting from the intersection of gender with one or more systems of structural oppression, producing a particular experience of violence that affects women and feminized individuals differently depending on their position within these intersections. This form of violence cannot be explained, addressed, or eradicated solely through gender as an isolated category.

Article X Sexies. Intersectional Epistemic Justice

Intersectional epistemic justice is defined as the existence, creation, and strengthening of collective hermeneutical resources with an intersectional approach, which enable the understanding and response to the situated experiences of individuals, groups, or communities immersed in interwoven structures of oppression. It implies the right to be understood through adequate conceptual frameworks that do not distort, conceal, and/or minimize their experiences and constitutes a necessary condition for truly inclusive and transformative justice.

Article X Septies. Substantive Intersectional Justice

Substantive intersectional justice is defined as the result of the substantive and procedural application of the intersectional approach when the parties involved are individuals, groups, or communities whose identities are shaped by the interaction of multiple systems of oppression. This form of justice acknowledges the structural and situated complexity of their living conditions, historically marked by the entanglement of categories such as gender, race, class, sexual orientation, and disability, among others.

Legislative Assessment**Intersectional Epistemic Injustice and the Absence of an Intersectional Approach in the Mexican Legal Framework**

Despite the amendment to Article 4 of the Constitution (DOF 15-11-2024), which recognizes the right of all individuals to a life free from violence—and establishes reinforced duties of protection for women, adolescents, girls, and boys—there persists an intersectional epistemic injustice that particularly affects the most vulnerable subjects, groups, and communities. As a result, the Mexican State becomes responsible for such intersectional epistemic violence, whether by action or omission.

A simple exercise such as counting how many times the word “gender” (35) and how many times “intersectionality” (0) appear in the constitutional text reveals the dominance of the gender approach in legal and policy design, as well as the complete absence of a conceptual intersectional framework that would enable its formal and substantive mainstreaming. If the supreme law lacks this approach, it is hardly surprising that state-level legal systems replicate the same structural omission.

This epistemic lag is also evident in regulatory and secondary legislation. The General Law

for Equality between Women and Men (DOF 2-08-2006), for instance, focuses exclusively on gender inequalities between women and men. Although Article 5, Section II, identifies structural causes of discrimination, it does not develop or incorporate a conceptual or methodological framework to allow the mainstreaming of an intersectional perspective. Section III defines discrimination against women as a distinction based on sex but does not consider the multiple ways in which such discrimination can be intensified by the intersection of other axes of oppression. This limitation is reaffirmed in Article 6, which reproduces the monocausal approach of white, middle-class, monocentric feminism: “Equality between women and men implies the elimination of all forms of discrimination in any area of life that arise from belonging to either sex.”

The Law for Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico (GG 06-09-2010) follows the same logic. Although Section IV refers to power structures that keep certain individuals subordinated, it limits itself to conceptualizing discrimination based on sex, without even suggesting the need for an intersectional approach. This contrasts with what is established in the Federal Law to Prevent and Eliminate Discrimination, which in Article 1, Section III Bis (DOF 04-12-2023) explicitly incorporates the concept of intersectional discrimination, defined as that which results from the combination of two or more prohibited grounds of discrimination, producing a greater effect than the simple sum of each of those grounds. This conceptual progress represents a turning point, although it still lacks clear operational tools for its institutional mainstreaming.

In this regard, it is worth highlighting General Recommendation No. 39 of the CEDAW Committee (31-10-2022), on the rights of Indigenous women and girls. This document makes explicit mention of intersectional discrimination and proposes regulatory approaches with an intersectional perspective.

Likewise, Article 5 of the Law to Prevent, Combat, and Eliminate Acts of Discrimination in the State of Mexico (GG 17-01-2007) recognizes multiple axes of subordination. Its second paragraph introduces the concept of “multiple discrimination,” referring to situations where people are simultaneously discriminated against based on various conditions, which nullifies or undermines their rights. Although the term “intersectional” is not used, the concept is clearly related and represents an interpretive basis that can and should evolve toward full intersectional justice.

Does the General Law on Women’s Access to a Life Free of Violence (DOF 01-02-2007) Incorporate an Intersectional Approach?

General Recommendation No. 19 of the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) defines gender-based violence against women as:

“Violence that is directed against a woman because she is a woman or that affects her disproportionately.”

Subsequently, General Recommendation No. 35 (which commemorates and updates No. 19) expands the interpretive framework and recognizes the intersection between gender and other structural factors such as class, ethnicity, age, sexual orientation, disability, migratory status, among others. In its words:

“Gender-based discrimination may be exacerbated by factors such as race, ethnic origin, religion or belief, health status, marital status, socioeconomic status, class, age, place of residence, disability, sexual orientation and gender identity, and migratory or displacement status, among others. These intersections increase the risk of suffering multiple forms of discrimination and violence.”

Despite this notable progress, the document remains at a declarative level and does not develop a conceptual or categorical framework on the intersectional approach that would enable its effective mainstreaming.

Implications for National Legislation

This situation constitutes a regulatory vacuum, not only legally but also epistemically, since gender-based violence continues to be approached as an isolated category, without recognizing the systemic structures that intensify and complicate the experience of violence for many women and people with feminized identities.

In Mexico, the General Law on Women’s Access to a Life Free of Violence represents a significant normative advance in combating structural violence against women. However, despite mentioning the intersectional approach (Art. 4, Section VIII) as a guiding principle, its content has not been developed or operationalized, limiting its effectiveness in contexts of complex and multiple violence.

The current legal formulation (Art. 5, Section IV) of violence against women effectively starts from a *ceteris paribus* assumption: it analyzes gender-based violence as if it occurred in a social vacuum, holding constant all other dimensions that shape women's identities (class, race, embodiment, sexual orientation, ethnic origin, disability, etc.). This

omission reproduces intersectional epistemic injustice and violence: it silences, excludes, and reduces the experience of those who live with interwoven oppressions.

In response to this limitation, we propose a legislative reform that explicitly integrates the concept of intersectional violence, accompanied by a minimum conceptual glossary to ensure its proper interpretation and application. This proposal is grounded in a robust theoretical framework, rooted in the contributions of Black feminism, decolonial

thought, and critical epistemologies from the Global South, as well as the lived experience of women and dissident people who inhabit multiple and hierarchical bodies and contexts.

This initiative does not seek to replace the notion of gender-based violence, but to complement, expand, and equip it with more powerful analytical tools that enable recognition of the specific ways violence operates when multiple systemic oppressions intersect. The goal is clear: to mainstream intersectionality in the legal framework in order to move closer to genuine intersectional justice.

The issue is not a lack of political will—as shown by former president Andrés Manuel López Obrador’s constitutional initiatives to recognize the rights of Indigenous and Afro-Mexican peoples and communities, or by current president Claudia Sheinbaum’s speech at the inauguration of the World Congress of Women Parliamentarians—but rather the absence of theoretical and conceptual development in Mexican feminist academia, which prevents the generation of a minimum, systematic, and operational corpus for the real mainstreaming of intersectionality into laws, policies, and institutional mechanisms.

Therefore, this initiative not only proposes a normative addition but a structural and epistemological reform that would enable the Mexican State to fulfill its constitutional and conventional mandates in the field of human rights, based on an intersectional justice that acknowledges and comprehensively redresses the plurality of oppressions.

Does the Law on Women’s Access to a Life Free of Violence in the State of Mexico (Government Gazette 20-11-2008) Incorporate an Intersectional Approach?

1. Nominal presence of the intersectional approach:

Article 3, Section X, recognizes intersectionality as an analytical tool to identify risk factors and conditions of discrimination faced by women due to poverty, ethnic origin, age, disability, sexual orientation, among others. This inclusion represents progress compared to other state laws. The definition is identical to that in Article 5, Section XIII of the General Law on Women’s Access to a Life Free of Violence.

2. Complementary approaches:

- Section VI of the same article refers to a “differential approach” that, while not explicitly naming intersectionality, alludes to the need for differentiated policies based on social conditions. This definition mirrors Section XV of Article 5 of the General Law.
- Section IX mentions interculturality as a cross-cutting approach, which can complement an intersectional perspective when the ethno-cultural dimension is acknowledged. This definition matches Section XIV of Article 5 of the General Law.

3. **Absence of a conceptual and methodological intersectional framework:**
Although intersectionality is defined as an analytical tool, no methodological roadmap is offered for its application, largely because no theoretical-conceptual framework supports it. This renders the term a declarative element with no clear tools for implementation.
4. **Gender universalism and ambiguity in the use of “vulnerability”:**
While the law acknowledges the diversity of women’s experiences, it does not break with the dominance of the gender perspective as the analytical and policy framework for addressing social inequalities. The use of the term “groups in situations of vulnerability” (frequent in Mexican law) tends to homogenize inequality without identifying the structures that produce it (racism, colonialism, classism, heterosexism, etc.).
5. **Weak or non-existent institutionalization of the intersectional approach:**
Institutional mechanisms (gender alerts, protection systems, public policies) are not required to collect, analyze, or address data using intersectional criteria. This limits the effectiveness of diagnosing and addressing intersectional violence.
6. **Lack of intersectional indicators:**
There are no indicators to make visible the intertwined forms of discrimination, oppression, and violence. Without adequate data disaggregation that includes intersectional categories (e.g., poor Indigenous woman, poor immigrant woman, poor non-heterosexual woman), public policy risks remaining homogeneous and exclusionary.

Conclusion

The State law represents a modest but significant step toward the recognition of intersectionality. However, it does not amount to structural incorporation or effective mainstreaming of the approach. It lacks a categorical framework to more broadly develop the intersectional perspective, clear guidelines for implementation, institutional mechanisms operating with intersectional criteria, and a reframing of the term “vulnerability” to reveal oppression as systems of power.

The Law of the State of Mexico must be strengthened with definitions, methodological principles, and institutional tools that operate from a true intersectional perspective.

Conceptual Framework

As shown in the legislative diagnosis, the Mexican legal framework exhibits a profound omission regarding intersectionality, which has led to multiple forms of intersectional injustice. It is therefore essential to define and operationalize key concepts such as

intersectionality, intersectional substantive violence, intersectional epistemic violence, intersectional gender-based violence, intersectional substantive justice, intersectional epistemic justice, and intersectional episteme.

I understand intersectionality as systems of social power relations that intertwine, producing oppression and/or privilege. I propose distinguishing between a *lato sensu* intersectionality—understood as the general interrelation of oppression and/or privilege—and a *stricto sensu* intersectionality, expressed in three specific forms (positive, negative, and hybrid). When focusing solely on the privileges it enables, I refer to it as positive intersectionality; when addressing only the oppression it produces, as negative intersectionality; and when simultaneously analyzing the combination of both, as hybrid intersectionality.

To date, the dominant use of intersectionality has been in its negative *stricto sensu* form. Although several authors have acknowledged—explicitly or implicitly—the possibility of the other two forms, they have not developed them in depth. In fact, the intersection of oppressions *stricto sensu* has become so widespread in academic and political discourse that it has come to represent the *lato sensu* definition of intersectionality.

The conceptual intersectional tripod I propose enables a dynamic relationship between different systems of power and overcomes the reductive victim/perpetrator dualism that white Western feminism has universalized through the premise: "all men are perpetrators, all women are victims." This premise dilutes, within dominant discourse, the situated differences experienced by men and women according to the intersections of their gender, race, class, religion, nationality, ethnicity, sexual orientation, age, etc.

In the model I propose for the three forms of intersectionality, I build upon Deborah K. King's (1988) interactive model, which asserts in her concept of *multiple jeopardy* that race, class, gender, sexual orientation, and nationality do not possess fixed, absolute, or arithmetic values. That is, depending on each person's situated position, even though these systems of oppression and/or privilege are interrelated, in certain cases some will be more significant than others, or may carry similar relative weight—yet always mutually constitutive.

Intersectional Episteme

It is the set of hermeneutic and reasoning resources that make it possible to understand, make visible, and address the experiences of individuals, groups, and/or communities situated at the dynamic intersection of structures of oppression and/or privilege. This episteme breaks with monocausal and linear analytical frameworks, proposing instead a relational, situated, and critical view of social reality.

The intersectional episteme diverges from traditional epistemological approaches that tend to analyze reality through isolated, monocausal, or hierarchical categories. In

contrast, it proposes a simultaneous, relational, and situated perspective that captures the complexity of individuals and communities shaped by multiple systems of power.

Whereas dominant epistemologies often produce knowledge from a universalizing perspective—frequently androcentric, Eurocentric, and middle-class—the intersectional episteme starts from the lived experiences of those who inhabit the intersections of oppression and/or privilege, recognizing their agency, situated knowledge, and the political nature of knowledge itself.

Illustrative examples:

- When analyzing the structural violence experienced by a poor Indigenous woman, a monocausal approach cannot grasp the multiple layers of discrimination she faces due to her gender, ethnicity, and class. The intersectional episteme can.
- In the case of Afro-descendant domestic workers, their precarious conditions cannot be understood solely through gender; it is necessary to integrate race, class, gender, and their historical position on the margins of the state.
- When a rural academic woman with a disability reports institutional exclusion, it is not enough to refer to academic sexism: the intersectional episteme compels us to consider how rurality, disability, and class together shape a specific structure of disadvantage.

Dominant Epistemologies vs. Intersectional Episteme

Social and legal knowledge—even in its most critical forms—has historically been produced from what can be called dominant Eurocentric epistemologies (of universal reason). These are characterized by universalizing, abstract, and decontextualized assumptions that tend to obscure the power relations involved in the production of knowledge. From these frameworks, analytical categories such as “woman,” “worker,” “citizen,” or “victim” have been conceptualized as homogeneous entities, ignoring the multiple ways in which race, class, gender, sexual orientation, embodiment, language, and territory intertwine to shape specific experiences of existence, exclusion, and/or privilege.

These epistemologies—often androcentric, Eurocentric, white, and colonial—have exercised a persistent form of intersectional epistemic violence by not only silencing the voices of subalternized subjects, but also imposing interpretative frameworks that distort or trivialize their experiences.

Against this model, the intersectional episteme stands as a transformative hermeneutic resource that recognizes the relational complexity of social reality. Unlike the binary and fragmented focus of dominant epistemologies, the intersectional episteme allows for:

- Making visible how different forms of oppression and/or privilege are co-constitutive and manifest simultaneously.
- Recovering the situated and lived experiences of subjects in their own voices, avoiding the distorting translation of their knowledge.
- Producing knowledge with ethical and political implications, oriented not only toward understanding but also toward repairing and transforming structural intersectional injustices.

In legal and legislative contexts, this episteme is not merely an analytical framework—it is a condition for intersectional justice and for the effective guarantee of human rights for those who live in intersectional conditions of vulnerability. Therefore, it is imperative that laws, public policies, and judicial decisions incorporate this episteme as a cross-cutting axis and guiding principle.

Intersectional Epistemic Justice

This refers to the creation, development, and/or existence of sufficient collective hermeneutic resources with an intersectional approach that enable the access to, understanding of, and response to the situated experiences of individuals, groups, or communities embedded in intertwined structures of oppression and/or privilege. It entails the recognition of the right to be understood through conceptual frameworks that do not distort, invisibilize, or trivialize their realities and constitutes a necessary condition for truly inclusive and transformative justice. Its absence results in intersectional epistemic injustice.

Intersectional Substantive Justice

Intersectional substantive justice arises from the substantive and procedural application of the intersectional approach when the parties involved are individuals, groups, or communities whose identities are shaped by the interaction of multiple systems of oppression. This form of justice recognizes the structural and situated complexity of the living conditions of those historically marginalized on intersecting grounds such as gender, race, class, sexual orientation, disability, among others.

Key features of this definition include:

1. It responds to a structural debt of the justice system toward intersectional subjects—something usually obscured by universalist or monocategorical criteria.
2. It links the intersectional approach to legal praxis, moving beyond discourse to demand concrete transformations in the administration of justice.
3. It recovers a relational and situated dimension: delivering justice is not the same as judging with neutrality.

Unlike gender-perspective justice, which mainly focuses on structural inequality between men and women under a binary and often monocategorical framework, intersectional justice recognizes that social identities are intertwined (gender, race, class, sexual orientation, disability, territory, etc.) and that such entanglement produces specific forms of oppression and vulnerability that cannot be understood or addressed in isolation.

Intersectional Substantive Violence

This refers to harm and/or damage—whether intentional or not, by action or omission—caused to individuals, groups, or communities by the simultaneous interaction of two or more systems of oppression, including but not limited to gender, race, ethnicity, social class, sexual orientation, gender identity, disability, or age, which affects in differentiated ways those living at these intersections.

Example: The violence experienced by an Indigenous woman is not only gender-based violence nor merely racism; it is a unique and specific form of violence that results from the intersection of those categories.

Intersectional Gender-Based Violence

This refers to harm or aggression—intentional or not, by action or omission—caused to individuals, groups, or communities by the simultaneous interaction of gender with one or more other systems of oppression, including but not limited to race, ethnicity, social class, sexual orientation, disability, or age, which affects in differentiated ways those living in these intersections.

Intersectional Epistemic Violence

Intersectional epistemic violence refers to harm and/or damage—intentional or not, by action or omission—caused to individuals, groups, or communities when attempting to understand and/or address their concrete experiences marked by multiple forms of oppression using theoretical and conceptual frameworks that invisibilize, misrepresent, distort, minimize, trivialize, or deny the significance of their precarious and intertwined realities.

This form of violence occurs when dominant analytical tools—particularly within monocentric, white, and middle-class academic feminism—fail to capture the multiple dimensions that shape the lives of women and people who are racialized, impoverished, disabled, queer, Indigenous, and/or Afro-descendant. In doing so, they reproduce colonial knowledge frameworks that exclude or subordinate Global South voices.

Examples of intersectional epistemic violence include:

- The use of homogeneous categories such as “women” without acknowledging the plurality of coexisting experiences and oppressions within a single embodied life (gender, race, class, embodiment, territory, etc.).
- The omission of racism, classism, or ethnicity as relevant factors when analyzing gender-based violence.
- The implementation of public policies that fail to distinguish the specific needs of Indigenous, Afro-descendant, or trans women, despite their overrepresentation in the most violent and precarious statistics, particularly in femicides, sexual exploitation, and state neglect.

Final Reflections

The absence of an intersectional approach in the current Mexican legal framework is not merely a theoretical or methodological omission—it constitutes a form of structural injustice and institutional violence. Intersectionality is not an accessory perspective, nor an optional methodological tool, but rather an analytical and political imperative to guarantee the effective exercise of human rights for those who inhabit the interstices of oppression and/or privilege.

The categories developed in this document—intersectional episteme, intersectional epistemic justice, intersectional substantive justice, intersectional substantive violence, intersectional gender-based violence, and intersectional epistemic violence—are not mere conceptual abstractions. They are theoretical and political tools designed to confront the structural inequalities that the current legal framework either conceals or reproduces.

Incorporating these notions into legislation, public policy, and judicial practice is an urgent ethical and democratic task. It is not only about naming what has historically been rendered invisible, but about transforming the structures that produce such invisibility and exclusion.

This proposal is part of a broader intellectual and political project: to decolonize knowledge, law, and justice from their monocategorical foundations and to build a more inclusive and situated legal framework that understands and protects the complex realities of people in the Global South.

Rationale and Justification for Legislative Reform with an Intersectional Approach

This proposed legislative reform is deeply grounded in the urgent need to rigorously and operationally incorporate the intersectional approach into the state legal framework addressing violence against women. As previously argued, the violence experienced by women located at multiple intersections of oppression (e.g., Indigenous women, racialized women, women with disabilities, non-normative sexual orientations, or those living in poverty) cannot be fully understood from a monocausal gender-based perspective.

From the standpoint of **intersectional epistemic justice**—understood as the creation and institutionalization of collective hermeneutical resources that enable the recognition, understanding, and response to the situated experiences of subjects or communities immersed in intertwined structures of oppression—a transformation of normative frameworks is indispensable. Such transformation must go beyond declarative statements or general formulations and must instead be reflected in **precise legal definitions, operational categories, and methodological principles** that guide public action.

In this regard, philosophical contributions concerning language and conceptual structures are essential. Ludwig Wittgenstein (1953) demonstrated that the meaning of concepts does not reside in an abstract essence but in their use within the various "language games" that structure everyday life. J. L. Austin (1962), in turn, showed that language not only describes reality but also produces it through performative speech acts—**to say is to do**. Jacques Derrida (1972) deepened this thesis by revealing that all conceptual structures are marked by differences, exclusions, and traces that involve power relations in the production of meaning. Judith Butler (1990; 1997) extends this line of thought to argue that language and normative frameworks are performative: they not only name identities but constitute them in the very act of enunciation. This implies that laws, legal categories, and public policies are not neutral; they contribute to shaping social worlds in which certain subjects are intelligible and others are not, where some forms of violence are recognized and others silenced.

This epistemological critique is complemented by Simone de Beauvoir's (1949) foundational insight in *The Second Sex*, where she exposes the false universalism of the concept of "man" and of Enlightenment reason, which present themselves as neutral, objective, and universal while actually embodying the experiences, interests, and perspectives of Western men—erecting themselves as the measure of the human and relegating women to the position of the "other." Elizabeth Spelman (1988), in *Inessential Woman*, further shows how even universalist feminist discourses have replicated this same logic by implicitly assuming that the experiences of white, heterosexual, middle-class women could represent all women, thereby **erasing the situated experiences** of racialized, poor, or culturally diverse women. Spelman denounces the construction of an "essential woman" that exists only as a hegemonic abstraction.

These critiques are central to supporting the need for an **intersectional episteme**—a framework that recognizes that neither reason, nor knowledge, nor legal categories can be conceived as neutral or universal without reproducing structural exclusions. As Miranda Fricker (2007) has argued, **hermeneutical injustice** arises when people lack the conceptual resources to articulate their experiences of oppression—or when such resources exist but are not institutionally recognized. Donna Haraway (1988), in introducing the concept of **situated knowledge**, reminds us that all knowledge emerges from a specific positionality, and that disregarding the epistemic positions of the most vulnerable subjects reinforces the hegemony of dominant knowledge. Sandra Harding (1991) contends that a feminist epistemology must begin from the experiences of subaltern subjects as privileged vantage points for critical analysis. María Lugones (2008) highlights the colonial logic of entangled oppressions, and Boaventura de Sousa Santos (2010) calls for the construction of an **epistemology of the South**, one that recognizes knowledges disqualified by the modern epistemic monoculture.

Integrating this approach into legislative reform is not merely a theoretical imperative—it is an act of justice. The law must stop being blind to the **intersections of oppression** and become a real instrument of transformation. Therefore, this proposal includes the definition of key concepts such as **intersectionality, intersectional violence, intersectional justice, positive, negative, and hybrid intersectionality**, as well as the **methodological principles of intersectional categories**, among others. Only through such means can we meaningfully **mainstream intersectionality** in the legal domain and ensure a life free of violence for all women, without exception.

Methodological Principles of the Intersectional Perspective

A) The Dynamic and Relational Nature of Intersectional Categories: An Analogy with Quantum Superposition

One of the foundational principles of intersectionality as an analytical tool is that social categories (such as gender, race, class, sexual orientation, ethnicity, etc.) do not operate in isolation or in a merely additive way. Rather, they are structurally intertwined in a constitutive relationship. This interrelational logic produces specific forms of experience, oppression, and/or privilege that cannot be adequately explained by a single category or variable. In this sense, **intersectional categories are qualitatively distinct from monocausal categories**, as their nature is composite, dynamic, relational, and situated.

In the model I propose—distinguishing **three forms of intersectionality** (positive, negative, and hybrid)—I draw from Deborah K. King's (1988) **interactive model** of *multiple jeopardy*, which posits that race, class, gender, sexual orientation, and nationality do not possess fixed, absolute, or arithmetical values. Depending on the individual's positionality, even when these systems of oppression and/or privilege are interrelated, some may carry more weight than

others or have relatively equal influence, yet they always **mutually constitute one another**.

For heuristic purposes, it may be useful to momentarily disaggregate an intersectional category into its constitutive components, as long as we do not lose sight of their entangled coexistence. However, this analytical operation should not obscure the essence of the intersectional phenomenon, which can be better conceptualized through an **analogy with quantum superposition**: an entity that is simultaneously all its components, more than the mere sum of its parts, and at the same time, separable into its building blocks like **qubits**. From this methodological perspective, it is possible that, in a given situation and from a situated observation, one component of the intersectional category may appear more determinant than the others. Nonetheless, recognizing this **contextual predominance** does not entail a regression to monocausal reductionism, but rather affirms the **interrelational and fluctuating logic** that defines intersectional identities, violences, and discriminations.

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